

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT CENTER (HRDC) IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

S. Joshua Benaiah*, T. Manimozhi** & M. Nasreen**

* Assistant Professor, Department of MBA, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** II Year Student, Department of Management Studies, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

Cite This Article: S. Joshua Benaiah, T. Manimozhi & M. Nasreen, “A Study on Effectiveness of Human Resource Development Center (HRDC) in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur”, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, Volume 7, Issue 1, Page Number 125-128, 2022.

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Abstract:

The report is the outcome of the project entitled “A Study on Effectiveness of Human Resource Development Center (HRDC) in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur”. The primary objective of the study is to effectiveness of HRDC practices of the institution and the secondary objective is to provide a evaluation about effectiveness of HRDC practices to understand the issues and challenges of HRDC practices, to suggest suitable measures for improving HRDC practices and to study students satisfaction level towards HRDC practices which need to improve the students for their better performance. The respondents of the institution, the sample consist of 150 students out of the total population. The data for the study was primary and secondary in nature. Primary data was collected from the respondents by means of a questionnaire. HRDC practices that aids the students to know their activities of HRDC department. As a result of the study, it was found that the students in the institution are satisfied about the HRDC practices, but they want some more modifications and additions in some areas of the HRDC practices like periodicity of the PDP hour, aptitude test, quantitative skill, technical skill, and reasoning.

Key Words: Human Resource Development Center (HRDC), HRDC Practices, Effective Methods of HRDC Practices, Satisfaction Level of HRDC Practices.

Introduction:

The Human resource development center is combining to some HRM functions, so it is a relatively modern term as the best means to prepare staff and organization based on activities (organizational development, career development, and training and development). Thus, human resource development center is a part of HRM, and it is the important strategies of the company due to playing role in improving students general performance to individuals and organization.

About HRDC:

The Human Resource Development Center has been established to contribute directly to the growth of the student. The HRDC will act as an interface between the industry and the students, and will primarily enable the students to select from their career options. We shall facilitate the selection process of all the companies as per human resource under the mentioned wide areas like.

Statement of the Problem:

HRDC is aimed at preparing student for future job with the institution or absolving institution wide problem concerning, acquiring or sharpening capabilities required performing various tasks and function associated with their present or expected future goal .The motive behind this study is to undertake and learn the impact of training and development program on the student of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur training cannot be measured directly but change in attitude and behavior that occur as a result of training .So student assessment should be done after HRDC practices session by the management ,to know the effectiveness of the training given to the student .HRDC programs are held by the improve the student skill, as well as to motivate the student.

Review of Literature:

A literature survey or a literature review in a project report is that section which shows the various analyses and research made in the field of your interest and the results already published, taking into account the various parameters of the project and the extent of the project. It is the most important part of your report as it gives you a direction in the area of your research. It helps you set a goal for your analysis - thus giving you your problem statement.

Rao 2019, in their research entitled a review of literature on HRM Practices in Education sector, private sector institution, regional rural institution and cooperative institution. The performance of any industry is dependent largely on the efficiency of its students and institution is no exception.HRM practices of Indian

private sector institution are marginally better than the institution in his study entitled „Human Resource Development in Education Industry.

Mehta 2018, in their research entitled -literature review on HR practices in education sector. There was a requirement to advance competencies i.e. skill, knowledge and approach among the students to make them more appropriate to the altering circumstances.

Objectives of Study:

- A Study on Effectiveness of the Human Resource Development Center (HRDC) in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur
- To understand the issues and challenges of HRDC practices in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.
- To suggest suitable measures for improving HRDC practices in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.
- To study students satisfaction level towards HRDC in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.

Research Methodology:

Research means a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. Research comprises defining and redefining problems, formulating hypothesis of suggested solution, collecting, organizing and evaluating data, making deductions and researching conclusions and at last carefully testing the conclusions to determine whether they fit the formulating hypothesis.

Research methodology is the specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic. In a research paper, the methodology section allows the reader to critically evaluate a study's overall validity and reliability.

Research Design:

A research design is purely and simply the framework for the study that guides the collection and analysis of data.

Type of Research	:	Descriptive Research
Population	:	3799
Sample Size	:	150
Sampling Technique	:	Simple Random

Research Instrumentation:

The main research instrument used in this project in questionnaires.

Sampling:

The aggregate elementary units in the survey are referred to as population. Here it covers the entire students of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

Sampling Size:

The study based only on the opinion and expectation of student. Total number of sample 150 taken for the study is respondents.

Sampling Unit:

Sampling unit is in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

Tools for Data Collection:

Primary Data:

Primary data means collection of data for fresh and for the first time is called primary data. The tools used for collecting the primary data are questionnaire.

Statistical Tools Used:

The commonly used statistical tools for analysis of collection data are:

- Percentage analysis
- Chi - Square Test
- ANOVA
- Correlation

Research Hypothesis:

A hypothesis is a specific statement of production. It describes in concrete terms what you Not all studies have hypothesis. Sometimes a study is designed to be exploratory. There is formal hypothesis, and perhaps the purpose of the study is to explore some area more thoroughly in order to some specific hypothesis or prediction that can be testes in future research.

Hypothesis I:

H0 (Null Hypothesis): There is no relationship between the gender and issues faced by the placement drive.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a relationship between the gender and issues faced by the placement drive.

Hypothesis II:

H0 (Null Hypothesis): There is a no relationship between the hosteller or day scholar and issues faced by the training session.

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a relationship between the hosteller or day scholar and issues faced by the training session.

Hypothesis III:

$F1 < F_{0.05} (6, 2)$. Hence we accept the null hypothesis that there is no difference between the questions and options.

Limitations of the Study:

- The HRDC practice is restricted in student only.
- The study on effectiveness of HRDC practices is completed in the specified period of time.
- The survey is based on the opinion of the student which may be biased.
- Since research has collected data only from HRDC in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Age of the Respondents:

Respondents of the Age Group Age	No of Respondents	Percentage
18 to 19 Years	35	23.3
20 to 21 Years	98	65.3
22 Years	11	7.3
23 years	6	4
Total	150	100

Inference:

The above table shows that 23.3% of respondents are 18 to 19 years, 65.3% of respondents are 20 to 21 years, 7.3% of respondents are 22 years and 4% of the respondents are 23 years. Thus the majority

Chi- Square:

Chi- Square test is the goodness of fit to verify the distribution of observed of the respondents is 20 to 21 years data with assumed theoretical distribution. Therefore it is a measure to study the divergence of actual and expected frequencies. The formula for computing chi-square is as follows.

Opinion Gender	Yes	No	Total
Male	45	43	88
Female	21	41	62
Total	66	84	150

$$\text{Chi-square} = \sum \{(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i\}$$

The calculated value of chi-square is compared with the table of chi-square for the given degrees of freedom at the specified level of significance. If the calculated value is greater than the tabulated value then the difference between the observed frequency and the expected frequency are significant.

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = (r-1)(c-1)$$

Chi Square Analysis:

Whereas, O – Observed frequency, E – Expected Frequency, r – Number of Row, c – Number of Column

Relationship between the Issues of Placement Drive and Opinion of the Gender:

Observed Values:

Solution:

H0 (Null Hypothesis): There is a no relationship between the gender and issues faced by the placement drive.

Expected Values:

Gender	Yes	No
Male	38.72	49.28
Female	27.28	34.72

H1 (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a relationship between the gender and issues faced by the placement drive.

O _i	E _i	O _i - E _i	(O _i - E _i) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² / E _i
45	38.7	6.28	39.69	1.03
43	49.3	-6.28	39.69	0.81
21	27.3	-6.28	39.69	1.45
41	34.7	6.28	39.69	1.14

Satisfaction of students is Test of Statistics = $\sum \{(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i\}$

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = (r-1)(c-1) = 1$$

At 5% level of significance table value = 3.841

Calculated value = 4.43

$$= 4.43 < 3.841$$

Hence, H₀ is accepted.

Interpretation:

Accepted Ho: Since the calculated value is less than table value the NULL

Hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is significant relationship between Gender and issues faced by the placement drive. Very important for intuition growth. The intuition should take necessary actions to improve their students' performance.

Conclusion:

A study on Human Resource Development Center in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur highlighted so many factors which will help to understand about their students and improve HRDC performance. The study was conducted among 150 students and collected information through questionnaire. From this study, conclude that majority of the students are know about the HRDC in their intuition. Most of the students are satisfied and agree the HRDC practices followed by the intuition. But the study recommends some suggestions like to provide availability of training period, so that students can get effective training. The intuition can still concentrate on specific skills are technical skill, aptitude skill, communication skill, and reasoning.

References:

1. Bhattacharya D.K. (2009), "Human Resource Development", First Edition 2009, Published by Himalaya Publishing House.
2. P.C. Tripathi (1997), "Human Resource Development", Third Edition 2001, published by Sultan Chand & Sons.
3. Bhatia, B.S., Batra, G.S. (2001), Human Resources Development, Deep & Deep Publications Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi.
4. Human Resource Management", J. Jindu, 2nd Edition Lakshmi Pubication.